

PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF INDIVIDUAL GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT, SELF-CONTROL

Turemuratova Aziza Begibaevna

Assistant, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Karakalpak State University
named after Berdakh, Republic of Karakalpakstan:

azizaturemuratova85@gmail.com

Seyitbaeva Uljan Sàrsenbaevna

Student of Karakalpak State University:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17430652>

Abstract: This study analyzes the main stages of individual growth and worldview formation of young people. It considers the psychological analysis of self-control and spiritual formation of young people. We also put forward the idea that overcoming psychological problems during the development of young people helps to increase their life experience. It also provides information on the spiritual growth of young people in a social environment, overcoming psychologically problematic situations, the formation of a worldview, and the basic rules for organizing psychological training.

Keywords: Psychological research, pedagogical approaches, psychological training, individual development, psychological diagnostics, psychological problems, spiritual development.

Introduction

The process of growth and development of a person throughout his life is a continuous, complex and multifaceted psychological phenomenon. The spiritual maturity of each young person is closely related to such aspects as self-awareness, realization of one's own capabilities, and control over one's own behavior. Self-control of young people is the ability to consciously analyze their own actions, feelings, motives and needs and voluntarily control them. In psychology, individual development and self-control are inextricably linked with the process of socialization of the individual, the culture of self-control and the level of spiritual maturity. Therefore, this issue is one of the important areas of modern psychological research. In psychological literature, the concept of "individual development" is interpreted as the process of forming and improving the individual mental characteristics of a person. According to scientists such as L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontyev, S.L. Rubinstein, B.G. Ananyev, K. Platonov, human development occurs in conditions of a combination of biological, social and psychological factors. Individual growth is understood not only as physical growth, but also as the mental, emotional, volitional, spiritual and social development of a person. This process is formed on the basis of the environment,

upbringing, family, education and personal experience. This study broadly covers the essence of the growth and development of a person, the factors influencing it, the psychological mechanisms of self-control, as well as their importance in the formation of the psychological well-being of young people. Self-control is a person's internal discipline, the stability of his will and the ability to consciously control his own behavior. This is a higher-level function of the psyche, coordinating a person's own passions, anger, feelings, intentions and actions. At the same time, the formation of self-control and attitude to criticism depends on various factors, and understanding the mechanisms of their interaction is one of the urgent issues in the fields of psychology and pedagogy. In particular, the development of methods for diagnosing and assessing these skills is an important task of the modern education system and personal development. This study analyzes the psychological foundations, forming factors, and diagnostic tools of self-control and attitude to criticism. Effective methodological approaches that can be used to develop these skills are also recommended. The results of the study serve not only personal development, but also further improvement of pedagogical activities. The development of self-control and attitude to criticism is an important factor in the success of an individual in social and professional life. The results obtained in the course of this study will help to further analyze various aspects of this issue and develop practical psychological approaches. The results of the study showed that the level of self-control is directly related to the individual's sense of responsibility and willpower. By controlling his own behavior, a person takes constructive steps towards self-development. The development of this skill helps students set goals and increase their effectiveness in achieving them. In the course of the study, individual characteristics of accepting and responding to criticism were identified. It turned out that people who perceive criticism constructively see it as an opportunity to improve their performance. However, low motivation for self-analysis was observed among people who find it difficult to accept criticism. Training sessions with the experimental training group showed the importance of interactive methods in forming a constructive attitude to criticism. In particular, it was noted that the participants' self-analysis skills were strengthened through trainings based on psychological diagnostics and analysis of problem situations. National values and traditional upbringing are an important factor in the formation of self-control and attitude to criticism. During the study, the habits of delivering criticism in a soft form and the tendency not to show personal mistakes to others were revealed in Uzbek society. This indicates the need to take into account national pedagogical

approaches in the formation of these skills. The results of the diagnostics made it possible to determine the relationship between the attitude to criticism and the ability to self-control. By improving these tools, it is possible to monitor the development of the individual and implement targeted pedagogical measures. According to the results of the discussion, it can be said that the development of self-control and attitude to criticism requires the integration of individual, pedagogical research and cultural approaches. It was found that these psychological approaches have a significant impact on the social adaptation and professional success of the individual. Consequently, the results of this study serve to enrich practical programs in pedagogy, psychology, spiritual growth and personal development. Self-control is the basis of a person's sense of responsibility, desire for self-development and the skills to effectively manage their own activities. This skill is an important factor in the personal and professional success of young people, and its development ensures personal growth and social adaptation. A constructive approach to criticism increases a person's ability to analyze his own mistakes and learn from them. This is an important motivational factor in a person's self-development. The formation of skills to accept and respond to criticism requires special pedagogical approaches. The importance of diagnostic tools: The use of modern diagnostic tools to assess self-control and attitude to criticism has yielded effective results. These tools make it possible to determine the level of a person's development and identify his achievements and shortcomings. The results serve as the basis for developing targeted pedagogical activities to develop these skills. National and cultural values have a significant impact on the processes of attitude to criticism and self-management. Therefore, the use of national pedagogical approaches in the formation of these skills is important. These approaches further deepen the psychological and social development of young people. Effectiveness of pedagogical approaches: Interactive methods, including role-playing, analysis of problem situations and thinking exercises, have shown high effectiveness in forming self-control and a constructive attitude to criticism. Helping young people overcome any psychological problems is inextricably linked to developing their worldview. It is important to raise the spiritual awareness of young people, broaden their worldview, and provide them with education and upbringing.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that the personal growth and development of young people based on psychological approaches can be considered primarily dependent on their spiritual growth. In trainings based on psychological

diagnostics, it is possible to eliminate psychological problems by studying the psychological analysis of self-control of young people. In raising young people as fully spiritually mature and perfect people, it is important to increase their worldview. The main goal of this study is to ensure the active participation of young people in psychological trainings based on their interests in their personal development.

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